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Abstract:

Experimental physics goals documented in form of presentations on Indico (Green). Contributions for Open Access proceedings publication with SN (Gold) approved. User community survey on R&D topics, priorities and collaboration potentials considering geographical distribution and topical complementarity launched.

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Delivery Slip

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1. PRESENTATIONS & PUBLICATIONS

The FCCIS (Future Circular Collider Innovation Study) project, funded by the European Union, represents a pivotal initiative aimed at advancing our understanding of particle physics through international collaboration and cutting-edge research. This deliverable, titled "Draft of the Physics Research Programme," is the result of a concerted effort by a vibrant and engaged user community. The programme has been meticulously developed to outline the future research trajectories and experimental frameworks necessary for the continued exploration of high-energy physics phenomena.

Central to this deliverable is the compilation of presentations, which are now accessible on Indico (Green). These presentations embody the collaborative spirit of the FCCIS project, showcasing diverse perspectives and insights from researchers across Europe and beyond. Each contribution reflects the collective expertise and innovative thinking that drive the FCCIS initiative, providing a comprehensive overview of the proposed research activities and objectives.

Furthermore, this work also culminated in the successful submission of the FCC Midterm Report informing CERN's Council Members and its subordinated bodies as well as the local and international stakeholders of this project. The CERN Council reviewed the work undertaken in a fruitful meeting on 2 February 2024. The progress in consolidating the Physics Experiment and Detectors chapter of the midterm report serves as basis for the final midterm report in 2025.

This draft serves as a foundational document, guiding the FCCIS project towards its goal of pioneering advancements in particle physics.

1.1. FCC PHYSICS WORKSHOP IN KRAKOW, POLAND

The FCC physics community gathered online from 22 to 27 January 2023 in Krakow to reflect the status and achievements of FCC Physics, Experiments, and Detectors studies and initiate new activities.

A key recommendation from the 2020 update of the European Strategy for Particle Physics is for Europe, in collaboration with the global scientific community, to undertake a feasibility study for a next-generation hadron collider at the highest achievable energy, with an electron-positron collider as a possible initial phase. The United States, following the 2021 Snowmass Community Planning Exercise, has also adopted this plan. The feasibility study for the Future Circular Collider (FCC) is currently underway. The 6th FCC Physics Workshop in Krakow gathered almost 200 participants. The meeting offered an opportunity to review the progress made in the feasibility study, strengthen the FCC community, and further develop the physics case.

As part of the feasibility study, the objective is to create a comprehensive set of solutions to maximise the benefits from enhanced statistics, a variety of experimental channels, and increased sensitivity to new physics provided by the new collider. The workshop addressed the requirements for detectors and progress in developing new analysis tools and methods for FCC-ee.

1.1.1. List of presentations documenting the experimental physics goals (Physics Workshop in Krakow)

The 6th FCC Physics, Experiments and Detectors workshop will reflect the status and achievements of FCC PED studies and initiate new activities. All PED Working group packages will be represented, Physics Programme, Physics Performance, Detector Concepts and Physics Software and Computing, as well as the joint FCC-ee Accelerator-Experiment working groups (machine-detector interface (MDI) and centre-of-mass energy calibration, polarization and monochromatization (EPOL)). Joint sessions and tutorials will reinforce the synergies between working groups.

The full list of presentations on Indico (Green Open Access) can be found here: <https://indico.cern.ch/event/1176398/timetable/>

Welcome and Opening			
Welcome	Tadeusz Lesiak	Polish Academy of Sciences	
Welcome and local information	Marcin Chrzaszcz	Polish Academy of Sciences	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1176398/contributions/5217136/attachments/2579883/4449640/Local_info.pdf
Goals of the workshop and plans forward	Christophe Grojean	DESY (Hamburg) and Humboldt University (Berlin)	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1176398/contributions/5232261/attachments/2579915/4449548/GoalsOfTheWorkshopKrakow.pdf
	Patrick Janot	CERN	
Overview of FCC feasibility study status			
Status of FCC Feasibility Study	Michael Benedikt	CERN	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1176398/contributions/5206796/attachments/2579934/4449584/230123_FCC_Physics_WS_ap.pdf
ECFA Higgs factory studies and FCC feasibility studies: synergies and complementarities (remote)	Aidan Robson	University of Glasgow	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1176398/contributions/5206798/attachments/2579932/4449580/ecfaHiggs_FCCws_Jan23_robson_v1.pdf
FCC and muon collider: synergies and complementarities	Roberto Franceschini	Rome 3 U.	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1176398/contributions/5206814/attachments/2579916/4449552/FCC%20and%20Muon%20Collider.pdf
US Contributions to FCC after Snowmass	Sarah Eno	University of Maryland	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1176398/contributions/5206817/attachments/2579662/4449477/Krakow%20USFCC%20Eno.pdf
Higgs			
Higgs physics experimental overview	Michele Selvaggi	CERN	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1176398/contributions/5206952/attachments/2580018/4449925/higgs_physics_exp_overview.pdf

Higgs coupling fits	Jorge de Blas	Universidad de Granada	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1176398/contributions/5206956/attachments/2580011/4449764/H_couplings_fits_de_Blas.pdf
Higgs to invisible (remote)	Andrew Mehta	University of Liverpool	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1176398/contributions/5208291/attachments/2580000/4449733/mehta%20(2).pdf
Geganbauers & Higgs Self-coupling	Ennio Salvioni	Universita e INFN, Padova	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1176398/contributions/5206958/attachments/2580033/4450373/Talk_Krakow_upload.pdf
Electroweak			
Physics Motivation	Gauthier Durieux	CERN	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1176398/contributions/5206964/attachments/2579937/4449806/durieux-krakow-23jan2023.pdf
	Tiann Tevong You	King's College London	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1176398/contributions/5206964/attachments/2579937/4450093/2023_01%20-%20Krakow%20FCC%20workshop%20-%20Physics%20motivation%20FCChh.pdf
The Z lineshape: a case study template	Alain Blondel	Université de Geneve	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1176398/contributions/5206973/attachments/2580136/4450013/Blondel-FCC-EW-LINE-SHAPE-2023-01-23-short.pdf
Afb (focus on discussion of systematics control and evaluation)	Giovanni Guerrieri	Universita e INFN Trieste	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1176398/contributions/5207217/attachments/2579967/4449663/guerrieri-Krakow-FCC.pdf
High-precision QED initial state corrections for $e^+e^- \rightarrow \gamma^*/Z^*$ annihilation (remote)	Johannes Bluemlein		https://indico.cern.ch/event/1176398/contributions/5206975/attachments/2579942/4449600/Cracow23.pdf
Measurement of tau polarisation at TeraZ (remote)	Jean-Claude Brient	Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1176398/contributions/5206976/attach

			ments/2580051/4449835/tau%20polar%20at%20FCC%20-%20meeting%20krakow%202023%20JCB.pdf
EPOL			
Status and prospects for the EPOL measurements	Guy Wilkinson	University of Oxford	https://indico.cern.ch/vent/1176398/contributions/5206995/attachments/2580229/4450670/Krakov_EPOL.pdf
Theoretical precision of luminosity determination at Higgs factories	Maciej Skrzypek	National Centre for Nuclear Research, Polish Academy of Sciences	https://indico.cern.ch/vent/1176398/contributions/5207008/attachments/2579820/4449596/FCCee2023Krakow.pdf
Status and progress on monochromatisation studies (remote)	Angeles Faus-Golfe	Laboartoire de l'Accelerateur Lineaire, IJClab IN2P3 CNRS- Université Paris-Saclay	https://indico.cern.ch/vent/1176398/contributions/5207015/attachments/2580506/4450693/monchrom_progress.pdf
Role of timing measurements in EPOL studies	Emmanuel Francois Perez	CERN	https://indico.cern.ch/vent/1176398/contributions/5207016/attachments/2580182/4450091/2023_01_23_BeamBeam_and_Xing_angle.pdf
Studies with dileptons: machine parameters and EW studies (remote)	Graham Wilson	The University of Kansas	https://indico.cern.ch/vent/1176398/contributions/5207022/attachments/2580469/4457166/FCCee-Krakow_V3.pdf
Software and Computing			
Introduction and statuts of things	Gerardo Ganis	CERN	https://indico.cern.ch/vent/1176398/contributions/5207131/attachments/2580637/4451195/FCC-SnC-Krakow-Intro-SoT.pdf
Key4hep and FCC software	Gerardo Ganis	CERN	https://indico.cern.ch/vent/1176398/contributions/5207132/attachments/2580639/4450929/FCC-SnC-Krakow-Key4hep.pdf
Analysis and visualisation	Juraj Smiesko	CERN	https://indico.cern.ch/vent/1176398/contributions/5207142/attach

			ments/2580635/4451322/fcc_analysis_and_visualization.pdf
Tools for Monte Carlo productions	Andre Sailer	CERN	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1176398/contributions/5207141/attachments/2580409/4450875/230124_sailer_fcc_dirac.pdf
Detector			
Introduction conveners	by Felix Sefkow	Deutsches Elektronen-Synchrotron	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1176398/contributions/5207146/attachments/2580794/445126/FCC-Krakow-Det-Intro-FS-20230124.pdf
Calorimetry	Roberto Ferrari	INFN Pavia	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1176398/contributions/5207147/attachments/2580673/4451101/fcc_phys_calodrd.pdf
Gaseous detectors (remote)	Anna Colaleo	Universita e INFN, Bari	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1176398/contributions/5207151/attachments/2580723/4451070/DRD1_FCC_v2.pdf
Silicon detectors (remote)	Nicolo Cartiglia	INFN Torino	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1176398/contributions/5207152/attachments/2580540/4451294/DRD3_FCC.pdf
TPC operability	Paul Colas	Université Paris-Saclay	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1176398/contributions/5207153/attachments/2580765/4451166/TPC-Operability-PColas.pdf
BSM studies			
Introduction conveners	by Giacomo Polesello	INFN, Sezione di Pavia	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1176398/contributions/5207156/attachments/2580991/4451635/intro_crakow.pdf
Exploring Z' models at FCC	Ben Allanach	University of Cambridge	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1176398/contributions/5207157/attachments/2580405/4450499/fcc2.pdf
Z decay and heavy neutrinos at FCC-ee	Biswajit Karmakar	University of Silesia	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1176398/contributions/5210782/attach

			ments/2580968/4451597/Biswajit_FCC_Krakow_2023.pdf
Electroweak phase transition	Simone Blasi	VUB - IDP (Vrije Universiteit Brussel)	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1176398/contributions/5207160/attachments/2581042/4451720/blasi%20FCC.pdf
SMET vs HEFT	David Sutherland		https://indico.cern.ch/event/1176398/contributions/5207163/attachments/2581534/4452687/Sutherland.pdf
Joint MDI/Detector			
Introduction conveners by	Manuela Boscolo	INFN e Laboratori Nazionali di Frascati	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1176398/contributions/5207169/attachments/2581141/4456610/230124_Introduction_MDI_Krakow_Mboscolo.pdf
Mechanical model of FCC-ee MDI	Francesco Fransesini		https://indico.cern.ch/event/1176398/contributions/5207170/attachments/2581219/4452078/FCC_Physics_Kracow_2023_Fransesini-Lauciani_24012023.ptx
Detectors integration in the MDI area	Franco Bedeschi	Universita & INFN Pisa	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1176398/contributions/5207171/attachments/2581129/4451907/Kracow%202023_v23_final.pdf
Status and Perspectives for FCC-ee Detector Background Studies (remote)	Andrea Ciarna	CERN	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1176398/contributions/5207172/attachments/2581018/4451674/MDI_backgrounds_ciarna-24012023.pdf
FCC-hh detector concept	Anna Zaborowska	CERN	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1176398/contributions/5207173/attachments/2580849/4451328/FCChhPhysicsWorkshop2023.pdf
QCD			
Introduction conveners by	David d'Enterria	CERN	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1176398/contributions/5208365/attachments/2581406/44524

			65/dde_QCD_FCCee_intro_jan23.pdf
Review of strong coupling at FCC-ee (remote)	Stefan Kluth	Max Planck Society	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1176398/contributions/5208374/attachments/2581279/4452596/fccee23_alphaS_review.pdf
Precision calculations at FCC-ee (remote)	Pier Francesco Monni	CERN	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1176398/contributions/5208389/attachments/2581503/4452644/FCCWorkshop_Krakow_2023.pdf
Monte Carlo challenges for FCC-ee and progress	Simon Plaetzer	University of Graz	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1176398/contributions/5208391/attachments/2581536/4452689/slides-reduced.pdf
Joint Detector/Software			
Strategy and plans for detector software	Brieuc Francois	CERN	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1176398/contributions/5208399/attachments/2581595/4452794/20230125_Brieuc_Francois_SFT_Detector_Plans_Krakov.pdf
ARC: progress update and plans towards full simulation	Martin Tat	University of Oxford	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1176398/contributions/5208403/attachments/2581656/4452921/ARC_Presentation_FCC_Workshop_Krakow_25th_January_2023.pdf
Modelling signal digitisation for test calorimeters: the CALICE experience (remote)	Vincent Boudry	LLR, CNRS, École polytechnique, Institut Polytechnique de Paris	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1176398/contributions/5208404/attachments/2581673/4453023/2023-01-25%20Digitization_FCC.pdf
Modelling signal digitisation for trackers	Riccardo Farinelli	Università INFN, Ferrara	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1176398/contributions/5208406/attachments/2581556/4452726/Modelling%20signal%20digitisation%20for%20trackers%20(2).pdf
Performance of an ALICE ITS3-like vertex detector for FCC-ee	Armin Ilg	University of Zurich	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1176398/contributions/5226882/attach

(remote) and progress on the IDEA vertex detector implementation in full simulation	Leila Freitag	University of Zürich	ments/2579873/4452684/IDEA_Vertex_Armin_Ilg_Leila_Freitag.pdf
Flavour/BSM			
Introduction by conveners (remote)	Stephane Monteil	Université Clermont Auvergne	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1176398/contributions/5208410/attachments/2581720/4453175/FCC_Introduction_Flavours_Krakow_20230125.pdf
Higgs and flavor (with a focus on FCNC)	Jure Zupan	University of Cincinnati, University of Ljubljana	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1176398/contributions/5208411/attachments/2581529/4453343/Higgs_flavor_FCC_v2_Zupan.pdf
Projections of CKM global fits and meson mixings	Luiz Vale Silva		https://indico.cern.ch/event/1176398/contributions/5208421/attachments/2581461/4452553/VALE_SILVA_v4_DF2.pdf
Top FCNC (remote)	Seddigheh Tizchang	Institute for Research in Fundamental Sciences	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1176398/contributions/5208458/attachments/2581891/4453347/Top_FCNC.pdf
LLP experimental perspectives at FCC-ee: ALPS and exotic Higgs decays (remote)	Giulia Ripellino	Uppsala University	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1176398/contributions/5208459/attachments/2581524/4452667/LLPs_FCCPhysics_Workshop2023_Ripellino.pdf
LLP experimental perspectives at FCC-ee: Heavy Neutral Leptons	Suchita Kulkarni	University of Graz	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1176398/contributions/5208460/attachments/2581820/4453258/Kulkarni_FCC_week_Krakow.pdf
MDI			
Summary of review on civil engineering and technical infrastructure requirements for FCC experimental sites	Mogens Dam	University of Copenhagen	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1176398/contributions/5208461/attachments/2581902/4453369/230125_CETIreview.pdf
Lessons learnt from CMS IR mock-ups (remote)	Andrea Gaddi	CERN	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1176398/contributions/5208462/attachments/2581689/44529

			81/MDI Mockup Proposal Jan 2023.pdf
IR beams losses	Andrey Abramov	CERN	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1176398/contributions/5208463/attachments/2581831/4453242/FCC-ee-IR-beam-losses.pdf
FCC-ee synchrotron radiation collimators and masks (remote)	Kevin Daniel Joel Andre	CERN	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1176398/contributions/5208464/attachments/2582066/4465159/Synchrotron%20radiation%20background%20@%20FCC-ee.pdf
Detector Stray Magnetic Fields	Nikkie Deelen	CERN	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1176398/contributions/5208465/attachments/2581540/4452696/NDeelen_FCCee_FieldMaps_FCC-ee_workshop.pdf
QCD			
Modeling of hadronization	Andrzej Konrad Siodmok	Jagiellonian University	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1176398/contributions/5207194/attachments/2582204/4453943/FCC2023_Modeling_Hadronization.pdf
Flavour jet tagging at FCC-ee with ParticleNet	Loukas Gouskos	CERN	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1176398/contributions/5207197/attachments/2582238/4453976/lg-jettagging-fccee-krakow2023.pdf
Tau			
Universality tests in tau decays	Lukas Allwicher		https://indico.cern.ch/event/1176398/contributions/5207208/attachments/2582275/4454057/FCC_Krakow_allwicher.pdf
Tau lifetime	Dr Alberto Lusiani	Scuola Normale Superiore and INFN, sezione di Pisa	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1176398/contributions/5207209/attachments/2582283/4605749/alusiani-fcc-krakow-jan23.pdf
B to K* tau tau	Tristan Miralles	Université Clermont Auvergne	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1176398/contributions/5207215/attachments/2582368/44545

			01/Talk FCC Krakow .pdf
On precise tau simulations	Zbigniew Andrzej Was	Polish Academy of Sciences	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1176398/contributions/5207216/attachments/2582272/4454329/FCCkrakow23.pdf
Quantum information and CP measurement in H->tau tau	Priyanka Lamba		https://indico.cern.ch/event/1176398/contributions/5207158/attachments/2582215/4453934/FCC_talk_quantum_information.pdf
IFNC			
Projects in Physics Programme and Physics Performance	Patrizia Azzi	INFN Padova	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1176398/contributions/5207218/attachments/2582489/4454778/IFNCTalk-FCCKrakowJan2023.pdf
Projects in Software	Gerardo Ganis	CERN	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1176398/contributions/5207219/attachments/2582538/4454565/FCC-SnC-Krakow-Opportunities.pdf
Projects in Detectors, MDI, EPOL	Mogens Dam	University of Copenhagen	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1176398/contributions/5207220/attachments/2582527/4457942/230126_ifnc.pdf
Activities in the different countries	Gregorio Bernardi	APC Paris CNRS/IN2P3	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1176398/contributions/5207224/attachments/2582532/4454616/2023-IFNC-All-Countries.pdf
Summary of activities	Gregorio Bernardi	APC Paris CNRS/IN2P3	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1176398/contributions/5207225/attachments/2582541/4454621/2023-IFNC-CONCLUSIONS.pdf
Higgs			
Diboson at FCC-hh (remote)	Shankha Banerjee	CERN	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1176398/contributions/5206959/attachments/2583051/4455563/FCC2023_Banerjee.pdf
Higgs/top interplay	Eleni Vryonidou	University of Manchester	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1176398/contributions/5207225/attachments/2582541/4454621/2023-IFNC-CONCLUSIONS.pdf

			tions/5208304/attachments/2583050/4455544/FCC-Higgs-top.pdf
Higgs mass and ZH cross-section	Ang Li	APC, CNRS/IN2P3 and Université Paris Cité	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1176398/contributions/5208220/attachments/2582987/4455428/2023_01_27_FCC_Physics_Workshop_Ang_Li.pdf
Higgs to hadrons in ZH with $Z \rightarrow ll/\nu\nu$	Giovanni Marchiori	APC, CNRS/IN2P3 and Université de Paris	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1176398/contributions/5208222/attachments/2582981/4456976/2023_01_27%20-%20Higgs%20hadronic%20branching%20ratios%20with%20ZH%20at%20FCCee.pdf
Electroweak			
Measurement of the W mass: the way forward (remote)	Paolo Azzurri	Universita & INFN Pisa	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1176398/contributions/5208210/attachments/2574382/4455909/azzurri_FCCwork27Jan23.pdf
GRIFFIN: A C++ library for EW radiative corrections in fermion scattering and decay processes	Lisong Chen	KIT	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1176398/contributions/5208191/attachments/2583129/4455900/fccworkshopkrakow.pdf
Synergies in top-beauty and a first look at b-tagging with exclusive decays	Lars Rohrig	Technische Universitaet Dortmund	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1176398/contributions/5226938/attachments/2583228/4455889/LRoehrig_FCC_2023_Krakow.pdf
NNLO corrections to H+Z (remote)	Qian Song	University of Pittsburgh	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1176398/contributions/5208194/attachments/2573117/4455466/FCCworkshop.pdf
Highlights and Future Plans			
BNL contributions	Marc-Andre Pleier	Brookhaven National Laboratory	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1176398/contributions/5226905/attachments/2582468/4454437/BNL-FCC-Krakow-Workshop.pdf

Future plans: physics program	Matthew Mccullough Philip	CERN	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1176398/contributions/5208308/attachments/2583297/4456036/FCCPhysicsWeek.pdf
Future plans: physics performance	Patrizia Azzi	INFN Padova	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1176398/contributions/5208309/attachments/2583435/4456581/PhysPerf-Plans-Krakow2023%20(3).pdf
Future plans: detector concepts	Mogens Dam	University of Copenhagen	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1176398/contributions/5208313/attachments/2583407/4456238/230127-Krakow-DC-Summary.pdf
Future plans: software and computing	Gerardo Ganis	CERN	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1176398/contributions/5208314/attachments/2583437/4494889/FCC-SnC-Krakow-Future-Plans.pdf
Future plans: EPOL (remote)	Jacqueline Keintzel	CERN	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1176398/contributions/5208317/attachments/2583152/4456178/20230127_Keintzel_FCCPhysics_EPOL_Outlook.pdf
Future plans: MDI	Manuela Boscolo	INFN e Laboratori Nazionali di Frascati	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1176398/contributions/5208320/attachments/2583245/4455936/230127_FuturePlans MDI Krakow MBo-scolo.pdf

1.1.2. List of presentations documenting the Experimental Physics Goals (FCC Week 2023)

The ninth edition of the Future Circular Collider (FCC) Conference, held in London from June 5th to 9th, 2023, brought together the international physics community invested in this visionary post-Large Hadron Collider (LHC) research infrastructure at CERN. Supported by the EU-funded H2020 FCCIS project, the conference served as a platform to examine progress and solidify plans for the future.

Leading experts from academia and industry reviewed the significant strides made towards the feasibility study's 2025 completion. Discussions centred on the exciting physics opportunities the FCC's integrated program presents. These included high-precision measurements of the elusive Higgs boson, exploring new particle interactions, and venturing beyond the Standard Model of particle physics. The status of R&D programs for cutting-edge detector and accelerator technologies was also a key focus.

Beyond scientific advancement, the conference fostered collaboration between FCC's collaborating institutes. It aimed to draft robust work plans for the FCC's mid-term review, presented later in 2023 to CERN's Council. Sessions covered a broad spectrum – physics, experiments, machine design, and the vital technological and infrastructural considerations.

The conference kicked off with a series of plenary keynote presentations. Renowned international speakers from science, industry, and European affairs provided an overview of ongoing activities across the study. This included updates on potential placement sites, the latest machine parameters, and an in-

depth analysis of the physics potential the FCC program could unlock. Parallel sessions delved deeper into specific areas, while satellite meetings addressed UK-related projects and the FCC study's governance.

The FCC Week 2023 not only charted a path for the next phase of the feasibility study but also served as an invitation to industry. Addressing the technological challenges represents an opportunity for co-innovation, propelling the project forward. The insights gained from the FCC Feasibility Study are expected to inform the next update of the European Strategy for particle physics and potentially benefit society in unforeseen ways beyond this scientific realm.

The full list of presentations can be found here: <https://indico.cern.ch/event/1202105/>

Physics case	Matthew Mccullough Philip	CERN	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1202105/contributions/5396847/attachments/2659371/4606360/FCWeek.pdf
Theoretical calculation strategy	Janusz Gluza	University of Silesia	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1202105/contributions/5396848/attachments/2659045/4606389/FCWeekLondon2023.pdf
Detector requirements from physics	Michele Selvaggi	CERN	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1202105/contributions/5396850/attachments/2659433/4606491/Detector%20Requirements%20from%20Physics.pdf
Precision electroweak	Christoph Paus	Massachusetts Inst. of Technology	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1202105/contributions/5397070/attachments/2660249/4608264/fcc-ee-ew-precision.pdf
QCD & parton showers	Pier Francesco Monni	CERN	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1202105/contributions/5396646/attachments/2660356/4608460/FCWeekLondon2023.pdf
BSM & physics case	Sophie Alice Renner	University of Glasgow	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1202105/contributions/5402635/attachments/2660011/4607826/FCWeekRenner.pdf
Higgs physics	Jorge de Blas	Universidad de Granada	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1202105/contributions/5396822/attachments/2660458/4609012/HiggsPhysicsFCCdeBlas.pdf
Flavour physics	Jernej F. Kamenik		https://indico.cern.ch/event/1202105/contributions/5402639/attachments/2660472/4608865/KamenikFCCWeekFlavours2023.pdf
Latest developments in FCC Analysis	Juraj Smiesko	CERN	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1202105/contributions/5402640/attachments/2660403/4608708/FCWeek%202023%20Latest%20develop

			ments%20in%20FCCAn alyses.pdf
General Higgs performance overview	Jan Eysermans	Massachusetts Inst. of Technology	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1202105/contributions/5396825/attachments/2661185/4610189/Higgs_Performance_FCC_Week_June2023.pdf
Higgs mass, $\sigma(\text{ZH})$ and self-coupling	Louis Portales	CNRS/IN2P3 - LLR, École Polytechnique	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1202105/contributions/5396828/attachments/2661170/4610858/20230607_FCCweek_Higgs_MassXsecSelfCoupling_LPortales.pdf
Higgs hadronic couplings and Higgs to invisible	Loukas Gouskos	CERN	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1202105/contributions/5396831/attachments/2661284/4610390/lg_fcc_eee_higgscouplings.pdf
In-situ determination of acceptances	Patrick Janot	CERN	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1202105/contributions/5396834/attachments/2661280/4610775/AcceptanceDiPhoton_FCC_Week23.pdf
Heavy quark electroweak measurements	Lars Rohrig	Technische Universitaet Dortmund	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1202105/contributions/5396838/attachments/2661296/4610415/Heavy_quark_measurements_LRohrig.pdf
Detector requirements from B to K^* tau tau	Tristan Miralles	Université Clermont Auvergne	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1202105/contributions/5396842/attachments/2661513/4610846/Talk_FCC_London.pdf
Prospects for b to snunu and requirements on the detector	Matthew William Kenzie	University of Warwick	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1202105/contributions/5396843/attachments/2661488/4610806/FCWeek.pdf
Detector requirements from Tau physics	Alberto Lusiani	Scuola Normale Superiore and INFN, sezione di Pisa	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1202105/contributions/5396845/attachments/2661200/4626683/alusiani-fcc-london-jun23.pdf
Detector requirements from BSM: long-lived signatures	Sarah Louise Williams	University of Cambridge	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1202105/contributions/5396846/attachments/2661263/4610332/FC

			Cweek-LLPtalk-070623-final.pdf
Detector requirements from BSM: prompt signatures	Nicolo Valle	INFN Sezione di Pavia	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1202105/contributions/5396849/attachments/2661352/4610694/FCWeekPrompt.pdf
Compton polarimeter	Aurelien Martens	Université Paris-Saclay	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1202105/contributions/5385365/attachments/2661851/4611544/FCWeek June2023 la sers.pdf
Polarisation studies	Yi Wu	EPFL - Ecole Polytechnique Federale Lausanne	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1202105/contributions/5390923/attachments/2661382/4611071/FCWeek Yi.pdf
Spin based beam energy measurements	Bastian Haerer, Edmund Blomley		https://indico.cern.ch/event/1202105/contributions/5396865/attachments/2661207/4610919/2023_06_fcc_week_resonant_depolarization.pdf
Center-of-mass energy shifts	Alain Blondel	Universite de Geneve	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1202105/contributions/5396866/attachments/2661653/4611155/AB-Energy-shifts-2023-06-07-v3.pdf
SC IR magnets system	Brett Parker	Brookhaven National Laboratory	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1202105/contributions/5408597/attachments/2659708/4607018/FC-ee SC IR Magnets System Parker.pptx
Magnet design for beamstrahlung photons extraction line	Carl Jaermyr Eriksson	CERN	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1202105/contributions/5390931/attachments/2660159/4608061/Magnet Design BSphtons Extraction Line CJEr iksson.pdf
Preliminary design study of interaction region crab sextupole for FCC-ee collider	Arnaud Pascal Foussat	CERN	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1202105/contributions/5385362/attachments/2661163/4611303/Preliminary 2D magnetic design of IR Crab Sextupole for FCC-ee Collider FCC week June 2023v3.pdf

Alignment systems propositions to face the FCC-ee MDI challenges	Leonard Watrelot	CNAM - Conservatoire National des Arts et Métiers	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1202105/contributions/5385355/attachments/2660154/4610129/FCC-ee_MDI_alignment_strategy_LW03032023.pdf
Challenges for the IR BPMs	Manfred Wendt	CERN	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1202105/contributions/5385352/attachments/2661130/4614377/FCC-ee_IR_BPMs.pdf
Depolarizer for the FCC-ee	Ivan Koop	Budker Institute of Nuclear Physics	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1202105/contributions/5396870/attachments/2662224/4612299/Koop-Depolarizer%20for%20the%20FCC-ee.pdf
The challenges of collision-energy calibration above the Z pole	Guy Wilkinson	University of Oxford	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1202105/contributions/5383622/attachments/2662165/4612187/FCC-ee_EPOL_aboveZ.pdf
Monochromatisation optics for FCC-ee lattices	Zhandong Zhang	Université Paris-Saclay	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1202105/contributions/5396871/attachments/2662119/4612100/Monochromatization_optics_for_FCC-ee_lattices.pdf
The roadmap to the final report	Jacqueline Keintzel	CERN	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1202105/contributions/5390928/attachments/2661538/4610923/20230608_Keintzel_EPOL_Outlook_FCCweek.pdf
Introduction to detectors	Felix Sefkow	Deutsches Elektronen-Synchrotron	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1202105/contributions/5433617/attachments/2662396/4612646/FCCweek23-Intro20230608.pdf
	Mogens Dam	University of Copenhagen	
Calorimetry R&D for FCC-ee and FCC-hh	Gabriella Gaudio	INFN-Pavia	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1202105/contributions/5396823/attachments/2662168/4612192/20230608_gaudio.pdf
SI tracking and vertexing R&D for FCC	Daniela Bortoletto	University of Oxford	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1202105/contributions/5396824/attachments/2662376/4612876/DB_SI_FCC_POST.pdf

Particle ID and Photodetector R&D for FCC	Roger Forty	CERN	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1202105/contributions/5402790/attachments/2662086/4612032/FCC-DRD4.pdf
Gaseous detector R&D for FCC	Maksym Titov	IRFU, CEA Saclay, Université Paris-Saclay	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1202105/contributions/5396826/attachments/2662446/4612774/2023_06_LONDON-UK_FCC-WEEK_GASEOUS-DETECTORS-R&D-FOR-FCC_08062023.pdf
Status of software for detector studies	Brieuc Francois	CERN	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1202105/contributions/5396827/attachments/2662524/4612966/20230608_software_for_detector_studies_status_BrieucFrancois.pdf
IDEA vertex detector in Key4hep	Armin Ilg	University of Zurich	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1202105/contributions/5396829/attachments/2662380/4613170/IDEA%20Vertex%20Full%20Simulation%20in%20Key4hep_PED_Armin%20Ilg.pdf
RICH full simulation in Key4hep	Alvaro Tolosa Delgado	CERN	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1202105/contributions/5396830/attachments/2662099/4612055/fccweek23_atd_v7.pdf
IDEA Dual readout calorimeter in Key4hep	Sang Hyun Ko	Seoul National University	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1202105/contributions/5396832/attachments/2662185/4612239/230608_FCCweek_shKo.pdf
FCC-ee TileCal simulation and reconstruction	Michaela Mlynarikova	CERN	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1202105/contributions/5396833/attachments/2662468/4613171/TileCal_FCCee.pdf
Tracking system requirements ALICE-3 versus FCC-ee	Didier Claude Contardo	Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1202105/contributions/5396836/attachments/2662437/4613297/FCLondres_DC_08062023.pdf

Si detector development for ALICE ITS3 and ALICE 3	Magnus Mager	CERN	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1202105/contributions/5396837/attachments/2662139/4612135/2023-06-08_FCCweek-ITS3ALICE3.pdf
Detector activities and plans in the US	Srini Rajagopalan	Brookhaven National Laboratory	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1202105/contributions/5396839/attachments/2662514/4612936/FC-C-Workshop-June2023.pdf
PED summary	Guy Wilkinson	University of Oxford	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1202105/contributions/5433713/attachments/2663312/4614501/FC-C-week-PED-summary.pdf

1.1.3. FCC Italy dedicated workshop

The recent progress and future developments of the feasibility study of the Future Circular Collider (FCC, the particle collider which could succeed the High Luminosity LHC project towards 2040), and of the other projects included in the European Strategy for Particle Physics will be at the centre of the workshop national “The INFN and the European Strategy for Particle Physics”, which in a month, on 6 and 7 May, will open in Rome, at the Frentani Congress Centre. The workshop will be dedicated to updating and discussing the activities that, within the Italian particle physics community coordinated by INFN, the various groups are developing for the implementation of the recommendations of the European Strategy. The two days of work will serve to start the process of preparing scientific contributions for the next edition of the Strategy, a crucial event for the future of European and global high energy physics.

The workshop organized by INFN is therefore part of the broader international context. In fact, last February the work completed so far was presented to the CERN Council, thanks to the commitment of the vast scientific community of which the INFN is also part, in particular for the implementation of the FCC feasibility study. The feasibility study is currently halfway through its development and should be completed by 2025. Furthermore, during the March meeting, the Council approved the general timetable for the next update of the Strategy. The deadline for submitting the community contribution was set on March 31, 2025, with the aim of concluding the process in June 2026, with the update of the Strategy by the CERN Council.

The feasibility study for FCC was launched in response to a recommendation in the 2020 update of the European Strategy for Particle Physics, according to which Europe, in collaboration with the global scientific community, should undertake a technical feasibility study and financial for an integrated project which envisages, in a first phase, an electron-positron collider and, in a subsequent phase, a high-energy hadron collider.

The strategic document identified, in fact, as a priority the creation of a Higgs factory, i.e. a machine capable of generating millions of Higgs bosons, with very "clean" final states, like those that characterize a lepton machine, followed by the ambitious project of a very high energy proton machine.

Thus, with the support of the Council, CERN has started the feasibility study for the FCC project, which involves the construction of a tunnel of approximately 91 km in circumference. The tunnel would initially host a very high luminosity electron-positron collider capable of operating at different energies, both at the production peak of the Higgs (ZH), and at the mass value of the Z⁰ boson, up to the production threshold of a pair of top-antitop quarks). The lepton collider would then be replaced by a proton-proton collider, with a centre-of-mass energy of up to over 100 TeV.

INFN is involved in various projects included in the European Strategy, and in particular in FCC through the acronym RD-FCC, with a complex research and development activity aimed at the creation of the IDEA detector (Innovative Detector for Electron-positron Accelerator), and also through the study of the infrastructure to be implemented and the design of the lepton accelerator.

<https://home.infn.it/it/news-infn/6518-l-infn-e-la-strategia-europea-di-fisica-delle-particelle-a-maggio-il-workshop-nazionale>

1.1.4 FCC US dedicated workshop

The annual US FCC workshop series started in 2023 at BNL with the idea of building and fostering the US community around the FCC, and particularly the FCC-ee project. We will have the second instance of this workshop at MIT in Cambridge, MA.

After the long and rich Snowmass process and multiple P5 panel town hall meetings, the High-Energy Physics community has come to a conclusion on what to recommend to the DOE and NSF about our future. The P5 released its report including those recommendations on December 7/8, 2023. This workshop will allow the US FCC community to come together and discuss in detail the recommendations of P5. The DOE and NSF will be invited to this meeting, and we expect a fruitful discussion.

Status reports will be given on the FCC-ee accelerator, detector, computing & software and physics analysis program including theory. In addition, we will host a plenary session for the expression of interest of US institutions for potential contributions in the areas of: the accelerator, the emerging detector collaborations, the physics program, and the software/computing infrastructure development. Particular emphasis will be on young investigator and student contributions to the ongoing FCC-ee Feasibility Study.

The workshop dovetails nicely within the general FCC schedule, preceded by the FCC Physics days in Annecy (January 29 - February 2, 2024) and followed by the summer FCC Week in June.

The Physics Presentations given during the workshop can be found here as Greek Open Access (Indico): <https://indico.mit.edu/event/876/>

1.2. FCC MTR REPORT

The landscape of particle physics has been profoundly transformed by two major developments: the discovery of the Higgs boson with a mass of 125 GeV and the lack of signs of new physics beyond the

Standard Model (BSM) in the TeV range after a decade of LHC operation. These findings have ushered in a new phase of exploration, marked by both clarity and uncertainty.

On one hand, the long-predicted matrix of particles and interactions described by the Standard Model (SM) is now complete. This theory has been remarkably successful in describing all phenomena accessible to collider experiments. However, as we transition into a new era of exploration beyond the SM, there is a notable absence of clear theoretical guidance—a situation unprecedented since the era of the Fermi theory. On the other hand, several fundamental experimental observations remain unexplained within the current framework, such as the matter-antimatter asymmetry, the evidence for dark matter, and the existence of non-zero neutrino masses. These unresolved issues definitively call for new physics beyond the present Standard Model.

The absence of LHC signals for BSM physics in the TeV range necessitates rethinking these open questions. Potential solutions may lie at even higher energy scales, which might require an "unnatural" value of the weak scale or an ingenious but still elusive structure. Recently devised new physics scenarios often involve light and very weakly coupled structures, whose mass scale (ranging from meV to ZeV) and coupling intensity to the SM (from 1 to 10^{-12} or less) remain unknown. This uncertainty calls for a new, comprehensive, and powerful exploration tool.

The FCC (Future Circular Collider) provides this tool by offering considerable advances in sensitivity, precision, and energy far above the TeV scale. Operating initially with electrons and positrons as the finest Higgs factory—and subsequently with protons as the energy-frontier collider—the FCC is designed to meet these challenges. The FCC aims to:

1. Map the properties of the Higgs and electroweak gauge bosons with unprecedented accuracy.
2. Conduct a comprehensive and precise campaign of measurements sensitive to tiny deviations from predicted SM behaviour.
3. Improve sensitivity to rare and elusive phenomena at low-energy scales.
4. Extend the direct discovery reach for new particles at the energy frontier.

From the Fermi interactions to the discovery of the W and Z bosons, and from precision electroweak measurements to the discoveries of the top quark and the Higgs boson, precision has always been a route to discovery. The FCC will continue this tradition, as any deviations from SM predictions observed at FCC-ee (the electron-positron stage) can be interpreted as indicators of new energy scales to be explored later at FCC-hh (the hadron collider stage).

Midterm Deliverables: Physics and Experiments

1. **Documentation of the Specificities and Complementarity of the FCC-ee and FCC-hh Physics Cases:** This includes detailed characterizations of the SM Higgs boson and the unique opportunities each collider stage offers.
2. **Strategic Plan for Improved Calculations:** To match theoretical uncertainties with the expected statistical precision from FCC-ee measurements.
3. **Preliminary Detector Requirements:** A coherent set of requirements to fully exploit FCC-ee physics opportunities and reduce experimental uncertainties.

Salient Conclusions from the Feasibility Study

The Feasibility Study has yielded several important conclusions:

- The baseline plan includes running at various centre-of-mass energies (Z pole, WW threshold, ZH production maximum, $\sqrt{s} \approx 4.18$ threshold), each providing unique and complementary scientific opportunities.

- Adequate flexibility in operation is necessary to accommodate future user community requests and unforeseen discoveries.
- The FCC-ee programme, particularly the TeraZ run, is highly ambitious both scientifically and technically, requiring careful planning and extended periods of data accumulation.
- The combination of FCC-ee and FCC-hh provides the most comprehensive and powerful exploration tool, with significant complementarity between the precision measurements at FCC-ee and the discovery potential at FCC-hh.

Conclusion

The FCCIS project's Physics Research Programme represents a strategic and well-coordinated effort to push the frontiers of particle physics. This work culminated in the final chapter of the FCC Feasibility Study Midterm report that is published on CDS: <https://doi.org/10.17181/mhas5-1f263>. An open access document will be published as part of D5.5 but access can be given upon request to members of EC and reviewers of the project.

1.3. FCC-PED INFORMAL FORUM OF NATIONAL CONTACTS

To unite the entire HEP community the FCC PED pillar has set up with the support of FCCIS WP5, an International Forum for National Contacts (IFNC) in 2021 (co-chaired by G. Bernardi/T Lesziak) in which the different countries can share the situation with regards to FCC and other future collider projects. In these last three years, the IFNC has grown to include national contacts from all European countries, and has reached out to all large countries outside Europe, with dedicated information/collaboration meetings (USA, Canada, Mexico, South Korea, Brazil, Argentina, Chile, India, Pakistan, to list the major ones). With Japan, there have been discussions, but no contact has been confirmed yet given the ILC revived initiative. With China since there is direct competition, only general discussions have taken place, showing however that Chinese physicists would like to collaborate if FCC would move forward and not CEPC.

To reach further consensus, inside each country, contacts for institutes which want to collaborate in FCC have been identified (>40 in the US, 15-20 in each of UK, Italy and France, 10 in Germany but growing and so on), hence a quite detailed picture of the FCC support is now identified, and is now showing a clear majority supporting FCC-ee. The minority is divided into:

1. those supporting a muon collider: many physicists of this community accept now that the muon collider is a second-generation machine, hence are not necessarily against the FCC project.
2. those supporting a linear option (mostly ILC-like) based on arguments which are sometimes contradictory.
3. those who would like to go directly to a FCC-hh, even at lower energy than in the nominal project, especially if CEPC would be built.

The FCC-ee IFNC has identified these physicists and participates in workshops in which scientific arguments are exchanged with them, and some physicists of the minority get convinced and eventually support FCC, but this is a slow process.

The strategy process on-going in many European countries to prepare the European strategy, is also playing a positive role to further unite the community. In conclusion, the FCC physicists are making an important effort to convince all their colleagues that the FCC project is the best for our community.

For the project to succeed, a coherent support of the FCC by the European particle physics community and policy makers is required. What further measures could be taken to strengthen the support?

- Support of the European Commission. A high-level event similar to that with the US should be organized with a strong statement of intent to be signed between the President of the European Commission and the CERN Director-General.
- Unequivocal positive statement of support from the update of the European Strategy for Particle Physics (ESPP). Ministries and funding agencies from Europe should participate in the ESPP process at all stages in order to be part of the FCC developments. This also includes positive support from the community through the ESPP Open Symposium and through ECFA & ICFA.
- Starting from the unequivocal support of the CERN Host States, build the support of the Member States, Associate Member States and non-Member States. The successful realisation of the LHC is testament to the strong and consistent support CERN received from its Member States & Associate Member States. CERN Council required significant support from Non-Member States, including the Observer States, before giving final approval to the LHC. A high-level event similar to that with the US should be organized with a strong statement of intent.
- Clarify situation with ILC. Given that a Higgs factory is of highest priority for the next collider, should the ILC not be continued, support should then be directed to the FCC.
- Set up governance structure that will encourage participation/contribution/commitment to the FCC. The FCC requires the long-term engagement and support of participants from CERN's Member, Associate Member & non-Member States. As the project evolves further, it is crucial to refine and adapt the collaboration model to ensure the efficient allocation of resources and sustained momentum.
- Continue building interest in the FCC through the engagement with communities world-wide through the FCC Global Collaboration (FGC) Working Group and the International Forum of National Contacts (IFNC).

2. PRESENTATIONS IN CONFERENCES

Dates	Conference	Number of Talks	Link
March 10, 2023-March 10, 2023	LISHEP2023 (Rio de Janeiro)	1	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1181208/
April 5, 2023-April 8, 2023	HEP2023 - 40th conference on Recent Developments in High Energy Physics and Cosmology	1	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1223490/
Feb. 17, 2023-Feb. 17, 2023	Heavy Neutral Lepton search potential of future HET factories	1	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1242038/
Sept. 4, 2023-Sept. 8, 2023	TIPP2023 (Technology and Instrumentation in Particle Physics) Cape Town	2	https://indico.tlabs.ac.za/event/112/
May 20, 2023-May 21, 2023	MelFest 2023 (Chicago)	1	https://melfest.uchicago.edu/
April 24, 2023-April 28, 2023	Parton showers for future e+e- colliders	1	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1233329/
April 23, 2023-April 29, 2023	Corfu'23: Workshop on Future Accelerators	5	http://www.physics.ntua.gr/corfu2023/fa.html
April 12, 2023-April 14, 2023	US P5 Town Hall Meetg - BNL April 2023	2	https://indico.bnl.gov/event/18372/timetable/#20230413.detailed
June 20, 2023-June 22, 2023	CLFV 2023 - 4th International Conference on Charged Lepton Flavor Violation	1	https://indico.desy.de/event/37920/
Aug. 21, 2023-Aug. 25, 2023	EPS-HEP 2023: European Physical Society Conference on High Energy Physics 2023	8	https://indico.desy.de/event/34916/
July 17, 2023-July 21, 2023	Lepton-Photon 2023: 31st Lepton Photon Conference	1	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1114856/

May 2, 2023-May 5, 2023	US P5 Town Hall Meetg - SLAC May 2023	2	https://indico.slac.stanford.edu/event/7992/
July 3, 2023-July 7, 2023	Beauty 2023: 21st International Conference on B-Physics at Frontier Machines	1	https://indico.in2p3.fr/event/28579/
July 3, 2023-July 6, 2023	CEPC-2023: 2023 international workshop on the Circular Electron Positron Collider	1	https://indico.ph.ed.ac.uk/event/259/
Sept. 26, 2023-Sept. 29, 2023	Brazilian HEP Spring Meeting 2023	1	http://www1.fisica.org.br/~epsbf/iii/index.php/en/
June 5, 2023-June 9, 2023	FCC Week 2023 London	12	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1202105/
Oct. 1, 2023-Oct. 3, 2023	Top Quark Physics at the Precision Frontier 2023	1	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1282455/
Sept. 11, 2023-Sept. 13, 2023	Higgs Hunting 2023	1	https://indico.iijclab.in2p3.fr/event/9063/
Sept. 26, 2023-Sept. 28, 2023	Dark Matter Studies in Accelerator Physics	1	https://agenda.infn.it/event/32756/
Oct. 31, 2023-Oct. 31, 2023	CERN EW milestones - 50 years of NC, 40 years of W/Z	1	https://indico.cern.ch/event/1301000
Oct. 11, 2023-Oct. 13, 2023	2nd ECFA Workshop on on e+e- Higgs/EW/Top Factories	13	https://agenda.infn.it/event/34841/
Nov. 28, 2023-Dec. 2, 2023	HQL 2023 - 16th International Conference on Heavy Quarks and Leptons	1	https://indico.tifr.res.in/indico/conferenceDisplay.py?ovw=True&confId=9003

2.1. LIST OF TALKS (JANUARY 2023 – JANUARY 2024)

- Nov. 28, 2023: [Flavour prospects at FCC-ee](#)
- Oct. 31, 2023: [An FCC-ee Forward Look](#)
- Oct. 12, 2023: [Precision absolute luminosity with photon pairs](#)
- Oct. 12, 2023: [Future e+e- collider measurements of the W mass & width](#)

- Oct. 12, 2023: [Interaction region design of the future circular Collider FCC-ee](#)
- Oct. 12, 2023: [Design of the IDEA vertex detector and its integration with FCC-ee](#),
- Oct. 12, 2023: [Noble Liquid Calorimetry for Future Collider Experiments \(ALLEGRO detector concept & ECAL development\)](#)
- Oct. 12, 2023: [Novel -hemisphere jet charge tagger at FCC-ee](#)
- Oct. 12, 2023: [FCC-ee Detector Full Simulation Implementation](#)
- Oct. 12, 2023: [Event reconstruction using ML for FCC-ee](#)
- Oct. 12, 2023: [Particle identification for the IDEA drift chamber using the cluster counting technique](#)
- Oct. 12, 2023: [CLD layout and performance update](#)
- Oct. 11, 2023: [Dual readout calorimetry developments towards FCC](#)
- Oct. 11, 2023: [BKtautau - B0 -> K0* tau tau](#)
- Oct. 11, 2023: [The IDEA Drift Chamber for a Lepton Collider](#)
- Oct. 3, 2023: [Future e+e- Circular Collider, detector design and top precision results](#)
- Sept. 28, 2023: [Future circular collider \(FCC\) physics prospects](#)
- Sept. 28, 2023: [New Physics Searches at Future Colliders \(from HL-LHC to FCC\)](#)
- Sept. 13, 2023: [Experimental prospects at FCC](#)
- Sept. 5, 2023: [The FCC project and its physics opportunities](#)
- Sept. 5, 2023: [The FCC project: Detector requirements & concepts](#)
- Aug. 25, 2023: [High-precision QCD physics at FCC-ee](#)
- Aug. 25, 2023: [Quark & Lepton flavour physics opportunities at FCC-ee](#)
- Aug. 25, 2023: [Exploring the frontiers of fundamental physics at the FCC-ee](#)
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